

Chromatic displacement versus spectral energy distribution

L. Lindegren (27 March 1998)

SAG_LL_016

1 Introduction

The chromatic displacement of images in the GAIA focal plane has been calculated for 175 different spectral energy distributions and three different reddenings. Simple odd polynomial wavefront aberrations were assumed. The calculations give an indication of how accurately the spectrum must be known in order to enable adequate calibration of the GAIA chromaticity.

2 Theory

A simplified calculation of the PSF for aberrated wavefronts was used. Only the along-scan pupil coordinate x (from $-D/2$ to $D/2$, where $D = 1.7$ m is the pupil length) is considered. Let $w(x)$ be the wavefront error. The detectable photon flux in the pupil plane is then proportional to

$$C(\xi) = \int_0^\infty \left| \int_{-D/2}^{D/2} \exp \left[i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (x\xi + w(x)) \right] dx \right|^2 Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda \lambda^{-1} d\lambda \quad (1)$$

where ξ is the angular coordinate along scan. In the absence of aberrations, or more generally if $w(x)$ is an even function, $C(\xi)$ is symmetric about $\xi = 0$.

Since the pupil is rectangular, the natural orthogonal representation of wavefront aberrations is in terms of Legendre polynomials of the normalised coordinate $z = 2x/D$. These have the property $\langle P_m(z) P_n(z) \rangle = \delta_{mn}/(2n+1)$. Thus, if the wavefront error is written as

$$w(x) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} w_n (2n+1)^{1/2} P_n(2x/D) \quad (2)$$

then the RMS wavefront error is given by

$$w_{\text{rms}}^2 = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} w_n^2. \quad (3)$$

The monochromatic Strehl ratio is approximately

$$S = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} w_{\text{rms}} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (4)$$

The piston ($n = 0$) and tilt ($n = 1$) terms are excluded from (2): the piston has obviously no effect on the image, while a tilt term ($w \propto x$) gives an achromatic displacement of $C(\xi)$ as can be seen directly from (1).

3 Assumptions

The quantum efficiency Q_λ and transmittance T_λ were taken as in SAG_LL_015, i.e. as for CCD#3 and a constant transmittance.

MMS assumes a Strehl ratio of 0.8 at $\lambda = 500$ nm. This corresponds to $w_{\text{rms}} = 37.6$ nm. Let us assume that half the power is in the odd aberrations ($n = 3, 5, \dots$) and, as a worst case, that all of that power is in a single odd aberration. Thus we consider $w_3 = 26.6$ nm (with all other odd aberrations = 0); alternatively $w_5 = 26.6$ nm; etc.

Using all 175 spectral energy distributions from Gunn & Stryker (see SAG_LL_015) and a standard extinction curve, $C(\xi)$ was evaluated in steps of 1/8 pixel in an interval of ± 3 pixels around the maximum (which, thanks to the orthogonality of the wavefront errors, is always close to $\xi = 0$). The correlation method described in SAG_LL_015 (Section 2.7) was used, with a symmetric template function calculated from the same spectral data but without aberrations. The PSF and template were not convolved with the pixel and TDI functions; this approximation will probably cause the chromatic displacement to be slightly exaggerated.

4 Results

Figures 1 to 3 show the displacement $\Delta\xi$ for wavefront errors of degree $n = 3, 5$ and 7 , as function of the $V-I$ colour index for unreddened stars. The typical displacement (or, rather, its variation with colour) decreases very rapidly with increasing degree. Thus $n = 3$ can really be considered a worst case. It is also noted that the displacement is not a unique function of $V-I$. This is not surprising as any colour index of this kind only samples part of the spectrum actually used for astrometry. At least part of the scatter about the mean relation is clearly related to luminosity class. The non-uniqueness of the displacement/colour index relation is further accentuated when reddened spectra are included (Figure 4). Using the colour index $V-R$ gives a similar result (Figure 5).

A more surprising result (for $n = 3$) is that the mean relation is not monotonic, but exhibits a minimum for $V-I \simeq 1.0$ or $V-R \simeq 0.6$.

5 Which spectral index should be used?

From a first-order analysis MMS has predicted that the chromatic displacement $\Delta\xi$ should be proportional to the spectral index $H = H(-6, -4)$, where

$$H(p, q) = \frac{\lambda_0^{q-p} \int Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda \lambda^p d\lambda}{\int Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda \lambda^q d\lambda} \quad (5)$$

and $\lambda_0 = 700$ nm is an arbitrary reference wavelength. Figure 6 shows the same data as in Figure 4 but plotted against $H(-6, -4)$. It is obvious that $H(-6, -4)$ is not a good predictor of the displacement. The reason for this may be that the location estimator

does not find the extreme maximum in $C(\xi)$, as assumed in the MMS analysis, but uses a wider part of the PSF.

The exponents p and q can be varied empirically until one finds the best correlation between $\Delta\xi$ and $H(p, q)$. Since the relation is not monotonic, the usual correlation coefficient cannot be used. Instead, the following statistic was used:

$$\epsilon = \sum_{i=2}^N |\Delta\xi_{(i)} - \Delta\xi_{(i-1)}| \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta\xi_{(i)}$ are the displacements ranked according to the spectral index $H(p, q)$. Using the displacements for the $N = 3 \times 175$ spectra in Figure 4 (cubic aberration), it was found that ϵ was minimized for $p = -3$, $q = -2$ (among the integer-valued exponents). Figure 7 shows the displacements plotted against this ‘optimum’ spectral index $H(-3, -2)$. The RMS deviation from a smooth curve is about $10 \mu\text{as}$.

It is seen that the reddened early-type stars of $H(-3, -2) \simeq 1.25$ deviate significantly from unreddened stars of the same $H(-3, -2)$. This shows that a single spectral index is not sufficient to model the chromaticity. This can also be seen by plotting the displacements for the 5th degree polynomial against $H(-3, -2)$ (Figure 8), where again significant deviations depending on reddening (and other, unidentified factors) occur. Actually, the RMS deviation from a smooth curve is now only $6 \mu\text{as}$, although the systematics are more apparent at the scale of this figure.

Another test of the usefulness of a single spectral index such as $H(-3, -2)$ is to look at what happens with more extreme spectra, e.g. with emission lines. The filled circles in Figures 7 and 8 show the displacements calculated for a mean quasar spectrum (Francis et al., ApJ 373, 465, 1991, as communicated by G. Gilmore) with redshifts $z = 0, 1, 2$ and 3 . The displacements are similar to those of reddened early-type stars with the same spectral index, or following an extrapolation of that relation. This indicates that the chromatic displacement is not necessarily a complex function of the spectrum.

6 Conclusions

A tentative conclusion of this study is that chromaticity modelling at the sub- $10 \mu\text{as}$ level requires at least two spectral indices, but perhaps not more than two (even for rather extreme cases such as strongly reddened stars and emission line spectra). The spectral index $H(-6, -4)$ proposed by MMS is not a good predictor of the chromaticity; $H(-3, -2)$ is better but not sufficient.

On the other hand it should also be recalled that part of the chromaticity (the so-called ‘constant chromaticity’) can be determined even without spectral information. This can be understood by considering two scans of the same great circle but with the spin axis pointing in opposite directions — the chromatic displacements are then opposite in the two scans and the mean positions would not be displaced. The present analysis would then primarily be concerned with the ‘variable’ part of the chromaticity, i.e. with the variation of $\Delta\xi$ as function of time and position in the field.

Figure 1. Displacement of the centre of the diffraction image (as defined by the image location process) as function of colour index $V-I$. A cubic wavefront error ($w_3 = 26.6$ nm) was assumed. The points correspond to the 175 (unreddened) spectra in Gunn & Stryker (see SAG_LL_015), divided according to luminosity type when available in Gunn & Stryker.

Figure 2. Same as Figure 1, but for a wavefront error of 5th degree ($w_5 = 26.6$ nm).

Figure 3. Same as Figures 1 and 2, but for a wavefront error of 7th degree ($w_7 = 26.6$ nm).

Figure 4. Displacements for the cubic wavefront error ($w_3 = 26.6$ nm) for the 175 spectra with interstellar reddening corresponding to a total visual extinction of $A_V = 0, 2,$ and 5 mag.

Figure 5. Same displacements as in Figure 4, but plotted against the colour index $V-R$.

Figure 6. Same displacements as in Figure 4, but plotted against the spectral index $H(-6,-4)$.

Figure 7. Same displacements as in Figure 4, but plotted against the ‘optimum’ spectral index $H(-3, -2)$. The filled circles are for the mean quasar spectrum at redshifts $z = 0, 1, 2$ and 3 (in the order from right to left in the figure).

Figure 8. Displacements for the 5th degree wavefront error ($w_5 = 26.6$ nm) for the 175 stellar spectra and four quasars, with interstellar reddening and redshifts as in Figure 7.